

Civil service of Pakistan: Ostracism of Women in Decision Making

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Abstract

This paper examines the representation of women in the Pakistan Administrative Service (PAS). Before the implementation of Article 27 of the Constitution of the Islamic Republic of Pakistan in 1973, women's representation in PAS was non-existent. However, Article 27 ensured women's representation in PAS. Additionally, the government introduced a 10 percent quota for women to increase their employment in the public sector. Although this measure was successful, the participation of women in decision-making tiers has been debated. This research was designed to study the trend of women's representation in key decision-making bureaucratic positions in PAS. The study analysed existing documents from three different sources. The data revealed that while the numerical representation of women in PAS has increased, they remain underrepresented in key decision-making positions.

INTRODUCTION

PAS, formerly known as the District Management Group (DMG), is a prestigious cadre of the Civil Services of Pakistan (CSP), established as a result of the 1973 administrative reforms. PAS primarily draws its membership from the CSP, which is itself the successor to the renowned Indian Civil Service (ICS) created by the British Administration in 1911. Officers in PAS are inducted through an annual competitive examination conducted by the Federal Public Service Commission (FPSC) every year (Ansari 2018). Candidates securing top positions in the Central Superior Service (CSS) examination are allocated to PAS.

Women's representation in PAS was non-existent until Article 27 of the Constitution of the Islamic Republic of Pakistan 1973 removed the bar on female participation in PAS/DMG under the clause of equal opportunity (Article 27 and Article 34, Constitution of the Islamic Republic of Pakistan 1973). Prior to that, recruitment rules did not permit the induction of women into PAS (Chaudhuri 1969). The administrative reforms of 1973 served to remove this barrier and allowed women to compete in the CSS examination for allocation in all occupational groups of the Federal Civil Service, including PAS. The 1970s saw increased participation of women in higher educational institutions as well as the labour market in the country (Ansari 2018). Starting modestly, women's representation in PAS in 2018 stood at 23%, with 160 female PAS officers serving across the country.

With gender equity and women's empowerment at its heart, the government of Pakistan introduced a 10 percent gender quota in 2006 for women in public sector jobs to provide an enabling environment for increased women's employment. This measure has been successful in increasing the number of women in bureaucracy, but full participation of women at decision-making tiers remains a long way

from being achieved in Pakistan. This fact has been reported multiple times in print media, but no empirical research exists to prove this for the elitist and powerful civil bureaucracy in the country. The current study, therefore, examines almost 40 years (four decades) of data from 1979 to 2018 and aims to address whether women PAS officers in Pakistan have attained passive representation (where they can participate in key decision-making bureaucratic positions and make decisions) or if their representation in PAS has only grown in numbers over the period.

Literature review

Although the term bureaucracy often refers to both military and civil bureaucracy, the scope of this study is restricted to civil bureaucracy. This chapter presents a review of the existing literature on the representation of women in bureaucracy and tries to elaborate on it in the context of Pakistan.

Women's representation in bureaucracy

Traditionally, due to the socially and historically constructed role of women, bureaucracy remained a male-dominated occupation where key bureaucratic positions have been held by the male members of the society whereas females remained under-represented (Aron 1987; Acker 1990; Guy 1993; Mani 2001; Kelly and Newman 2001; Stivers 2002; Macarie 2010; Ballard 2015). During the past years, several studies have been conducted to present the social, cultural, and organizational explanations for men's and women's unequal access to important bureaucratic positions. They expose the influence of organizational, cultural, and social norms that are gender biased and lead to gendered career inequalities for women bureaucrats (Kanter 1977; Ferguson 1984; Gadéa and Marry 2000; Wajcman 2003; Alkadry and Tower 2014; Revillard et al. 2018).

Research regarding women working in the male-dominated occupations surfaced in the 1970s (Epstein 1970; Kissel and Katsampes 1980) that documented potential benefits and impacts of women's employment. Literature in the proceeding years recognizes the importance of female employment in the public bureaucracy and indicates its positive outcomes such as the representation of marginalized women in bureaucratic policymaking and implementation (Stanley 1989; Dolan 2000; Keiser et al. 2002; Wilkins 2006; Park 2013; Meier and Funk 2017; Song 2018). However, this literature primarily focuses on Western and developed countries (the Global North), and there is a scarcity of literature to establish the facts for underdeveloped and developing countries in the Global South.

Pakistan, a developing country from the South Asian region, has strong and influential bureaucratic institutions (Hussain and Kokab 2013). The existing system of civil bureaucracy in Pakistan retains a fundamental continuity with the past. The hierarchical structure and executive rule by a very powerful bureaucracy in the country has a colonial legacy. During the British Raj, colonial administrators in the United India established powerful and extremely centralized bureaucratic institutions, controlled by the ICS (Wilder 2009). The prestigious and very powerful ICS was structurally masculine, and there were no women in the ICS (Ferdous, 2014). After independence in 1947, the CSP continued the legacy of ICS and the equality of opportunity for females was denied.

The candidature for the All-Pakistan Service (now, PAS) was reserved only for male candidates. Women were not allowed to join the prestigious All Pakistan Service as the recruitment rules for civil service allowed induction of women only in the Audit and Accounts Service, Military Accounts Service, Railways Account Service, Income Tax Service and Postal Service. The main logic

behind this rule

was a perception that females are not suitable for extensive field visits, district administration, to maintain law and order and to collect land revenue (Chaudhuri 1969). Due to this restriction, the disparity between male and female representation in bureaucracy grew manifold as women were restricted to desk jobs (Mahtab 1995). This restriction lasted till 1973 when Article 27 of Pakistan's constitution provided an equal opportunity for women's recruitment in all civil service groups (Kabir 2013). The post-1973 trend of women's participation in civil service and especially in PAS is not documented much in the literature, which is an interesting area of investigation.

The constitutional guarantee in the 1973's Constitution of the Islamic Republic of Pakistan that "no citizen, who otherwise qualifies for appointment, shall not be discriminated against any such appointment based on gender" (Article 27, Constitution of Islamic Republic of Pakistan 1973) opened long closed doors of entry for women in bureaucracy. Also, being a signatory to the Beijing Platform for Action, Pakistan has committed to taking all necessary measures to ensure women's equal access and full participation in decision-making roles as well as to build women's ability to compete for decision-making positions. To achieve these objectives, Pakistan pledged a goal of gender balance in governmental bodies and committees, the judiciary, and in all governmental and public administration positions (Rai et al. 2007).

Improving women's representation through gender quotas

To address gender imbalance in various governing institutions, a policy of gender quota is implemented by setting aside a certain number of seats for women in politics and public sector organizations (Hills 2015). In this regard, the UN World Women's Conference in

Beijing in 1995 provided legitimacy for quota claims being put forward by national women's organizations and groups. This growing international trend of gender quotas is considered the "fast track" to equal representation of women to that of men (Dahlerup and Freidenvall 2005). Globally, different types of gender quotas have been introduced in political institutions and government organizations (Ford and Rohini 2011). Quota systems are viewed as one of the most effective policies to increase women's passive representation in bureaucracy. There is some evidence in research that ascertains that number matters in bureaucracy, as numbers make women visible. This leads to an understanding that attaining a critical mass through gender quotas leads to improvement in the numerical representation of women in bureaucracy. However, understanding passive representation through gender quota needs empirical evidence. EY's Index on Women as Public Sector Leaders highlights the fact that despite several initiatives, female leadership in the public administration sector remains restricted in many developing countries (Schreiber 2013). Many developing countries have implemented gender quotas in the public sector and have been successful in improving the numbers for women's representation. However, evidence needs to explore if it has been translated into a real/substantive passive representation where women have full participation rights just like their male colleagues.

According to the 2007 UNDP's report, the percentage of women in administrative and managerial roles in Pakistan in 1998 was 8 percent, which remained 8.7 percent till 2002 (Rai et al. 2007). This situation alarmed the government of Pakistan, and it introduced a 10 percent gender quota in the Civil Services of Pakistan as a strategy to address gender disparities and to encourage women's representation in public offices in leadership positions (UNDP 2017). It is considered an

effective strategy

as it has improved women's representation in CSP. Despite the presence of a larger number of women bureaucrats in Pakistan's bureaucracy, it is often reported that a very small number of female bureaucrats are serving in key bureaucratic positions (Fatima 2017).

Why is representative bureaucracy important?

Understanding the significance of bureaucracy, scholars suggest an inclusive and representative bureaucracy as a practical means to achieve bureaucratic responsiveness in a society. The concept of representative bureaucracy was first developed by Donald Kingsley in 1944 and was later defined and interpreted in several ways by different scholars (Meier 2018). Although Kingsley coined the concept of representative bureaucracy, it was Mosher who further advanced and explained the theory of representative bureaucracy by differentiating between passive representation and active representation. This distinction has structured the subsequent research and most of the literature in the field revolves around this distinction (Lim 2006).

According to Mosher, passive representation occurs when bureaucracy includes individuals from specified groups, such as racial and ethnic minorities and women within its ranks to the share of its population (Johnston and Houston 2018). Whereas active representation occurs when a bureaucrat ensures (intentionally or unintentionally) that the interests of individuals who share his/her demographic identity (gender, race, ethnicity) are not overlooked in policy decision making and implementation (Bradbury and Kellough 2011). Active representation is more concerned with how representation influences the process of policymaking, starting from policymaking to its design and implementation (Wilkins 2006) where bureaucrats try or ensure

that policy decisions benefit citizens who share the same demographic and social background with them (Hindera 1993; Keiser et al. 2002; Sowa and Selden 2003). Thus, the more demographically representative a bureaucracy is in terms of passive representation, the more likely it will translate into active representation and will benefit the relevant demographic group (Thielemann and Stewart 1996). A rich literature exists that explores and affirms this fact for race, ethnicity and region with a growing focus on empirical research. A few of them study impact of race in the Equal Employment Opportunity Commission (Hindera 1993), in education sector (Pitts 2007; Rocha and Hawes 2009), impact of region on representation behaviour (Grissom et al. 2009) and influence of passive representation in the selection of contractors (Brunjes and Kellough 2018). In contrast, research highlighting the representation and the sex of the bureaucrats is scant and needs insight into the subject (Keiser et al. 2002).

From the literature discussed in this section of the study, it is concluded that a mere numerical increase in women's representation cannot be called passive representation unless women have equal and full participation in bureaucracy. Currently, research in the field does not empirically examine this observation for the high echelons of bureaucratic power in underdeveloped countries, especially in a country like Pakistan, and hence, it provided sufficient inspiration for the researcher to undertake this study.

Research methodology

Representation of women in the influential cadre of Pakistan's bureaucracy i.e., PAS, has always been a matter of debate. Women have either been given no representation or less representation in PAS. However, different strategies have been adopted at different times to ensure equal opportunities for women in this special cadre of bureaucracy. Still, the representation of women in PAS and the

effectiveness of strategies (to ensure women's representation in PAS) is running a public debate. To study the women's representation in the influential cadre of Pakistan's bureaucracy, a nonreactive document analysis was performed. Document analysis or document review is an appropriate research method in cases where the information is already available within the organization in the form of a document (Neuman 2006). In case of our current study, the data regarding the selection and allocation of all PAS officers were available at the Civil Services Academy, PAS Campus Lahore and Provincial Services and General Administration departments. We, therefore, found document analysis an appropriate research method to investigate the topic.

Data source and data collection

Data was collected through allocation lists provided by the Civil Services Academy, PAS Campus Lahore and through pro-formas filled by Provincial Services and General Administration Departments and Establishment Division, Islamabad. The data was collected from 41 specialized training programs (STP) spread over 40 years to determine the trend of women's participation ever since the constitutional provision allowed women to join PAS.

Data was collected from the three mentioned sources through different techniques. The first set of data was collected from lists of PAS officers provided by the Civil Services Academy, PAS Campus Lahore. PAS Campus Lahore is the alma mater of PAS officers, where their mandatory STP is conducted. Therefore, it was a reliable source of data as they have the data of all the officers who have been inducted in PAS. For this study, lists of PAS officers for almost four decades (1979-2018) were obtained and male and female representation (numerical) was extracted to determine a yearly trend of women's representation in PAS. The period was chosen

because after the 1973 Constitution of Pakistan removed the bar on women aspirants to join PAS, the first STP of PAS was conducted in 1979.

The second batch of data was collected by developing pro-forma A. This was designed to gather the total number of females that have been inducted into PAS on the basis of a 10 percent gender quota, 2006. The filled pro-forma containing information of women candidates benefiting from the 10 percent gender quota 2006, in their respective Civil Services examination year, was obtained through email from Training wing T-5, Establishment Division, Islamabad. This wing is responsible for allocating successful candidates of the CSS examination into PAS. Therefore, the data provided by them was a credible source to assess the impact of a 10 percent Gender quota, 2006 for PAS. The list was studied and compared with the list of PAS officers provided by the PAS Campus, Lahore. The data was then compiled in a tabular form to examine the role of a 10 percent gender quota.

The third and final batch of data was collected through pro-forma B, which was developed to collect data on the representation of women PAS officers in key bureaucratic positions across the country. Pro forma-B was designed and then sent electronically (via email and WhatsApp) to the provincial services and General Administration departments of all four provinces, Gilgit-Baltistan region and E-5 wing, Establishment Division, Islamabad. These offices deal with transfers and postings of PAS officers across the country. The purpose was to identify the representation of women PAS officers in key decision-making positions from the PAS career path. The results were useful to understand whether women in PAS have only grown in number or do they have passive representation in PAS that is to have full participation at all levels of the PAS career path. Data from the provinces is then compiled in a chart form (millennials) to

explain the disparity in women's representation in key decision-making positions across the country.

Data analysis

The numerical data was obtained from the lists of PAS officers provided by the civil service academy and through the use of pro-forma (A and B). Initially, the total numbers of female PAS officers were calculated and identified from 1979 to 2018. The whole data about the numbers of women PAS were then arranged in the form of a table (Table 1). Then, the number of women PAS who were inducted into the service after the enactment of the 10% gender quota was calculated. This statistical data was taken from the pro-forma and the statistical data is arranged in the form of a table (Table 2). Similarly, the numbers of women in key bureaucratic positions in different provinces were calculated (which were also taken while using the pro-forma from the concerned departments) and presented in respective tables in the result section. The statistical/numerical values present in the table were interpreted to generate the result of the study.

Limitations

Despite achieving the aim of the study, some limitations were unavoidable. Being a woman PAS officer (first author), I put aside my experience and personal beliefs during data collection and its analysis. However, I still believe it may add to the limitation of the study. Secondly, since officers of PAS on junior ranks (such as AC and DC) are usually not transferred to Azad Jammu and Kashmir, therefore, data from this region of Pakistan was not included for the study.

Significance of the study

The findings of this research can be of interest to policymakers regarding reforms to take necessary measures to ensure gender inclusive bureaucracies in developing countries. Secondly, this study contributes to the

emerging literature on representative bureaucracy in the underdeveloped and developing world.

Results

In this section, we have shared results for the representation of women in the elitist cadre of Pakistan’s bureaucracy that is PAS. The themes discussed in this section include the trend of women's representation in PAS from 1979 to 2018, the impact of the 10 percent gender quota on the overall representation of women in PAS, and the analysis of whether women in PAS have the right to full participation like their male counterparts.

Trends of women's representation in PAS

In order to understand whether women in PAS have achieved passive representation or not, this study was conducted. Through Table 1, the trend of women's representation in PAS has been discussed. It studied data of probationary officers (both male and female) inducted in PAS from 1979 to 2018.

Table 1: Numerical representation of women in Pakistan Administrative Service, PAS (1979-2018)

SPECIALIZED TRAINING PROGRAM (STP)	NUMBER OF PAS OFFICERS	NUMBER OF MALE PAS OFFICERS	NUMBER OF FEMALE PAS OFFICERS	RATIO OF FEMALE PAS OFFICERS TO TOTAL PAS OFFICERS	RATIO OF FEMALE PAS OFFICERS TO TOTAL NUMBER OF PAS OFFICERS
1st	1979	20	19	1/9	15%
2nd	1988	24	22	2/2	18%
3rd	1988	33	31	3/2	26%
4th	1982	44	43	4/1	12%
5th	1983	44	42	4/2	15%
6th	1985	47	47	0/0	0%
7th	1986	39	38	3/1	13%
8th	1987	40	38	3/2	15%
9th	1988	31	29	2/2	26%
10th	1989	39	39	0/0	0%
11th	1989	33	33	0/0	0%

					OFFICERS)
1st	1979	20	19	1	15%
2nd	1988	24	22	2	18%
3rd	1988	33	31	2	26%
4th	1982	44	43	1	12%
5th	1983	44	42	2	15%
6th	1985	47	47	0	0%
7th	1986	39	38	1	13%
8th	1987	40	38	2	15%
9th	1988	31	29	2	26%
10th	1989	39	39	0	0%
11th	1989	33	33	0	0%

	9 9 0	0	0		/ % 30
12th	1 9 9 1	2 0	1 9	1	15 / % 20
13th	1 9 9 2	3 6	3 4	2	16 / % 18
14th	1 9 9 2	3 0	2 5	5	117 / % 6
15th	1 9 9 3	1 9	1 9	0	00 / % 19
16th	1 9 9 4	2 1	2 1	0	00 / % 21
17th	1 9 9 4	1 3	1 0	3	323 / % 13
18th	1 9 9 5	2 6	2 5	1	14 / % 26
19th	1 9 9 6	2 6	2 4	2	18 / % 13
20th	1 9 9 7	2 6	2 3	3	312 / % 26
21st	1 9 9 8	2 7	2 4	3	111 / % 9
22nd	1 9	1 9	1 8	1	15 / %

	9 9 0				19
23rd	2 0 0 0	2 1	2 0	1	14 / % 21
24th	2 0 0 3	2 2	2 0	2	19 / % 11
25th	2 0 0 4	1 0	1 0	0	00 / % 10
26th	2 0 0 5	1 8	1 8	1	16 / % 18
27th	2 0 0 6	2 8	2 4	4	114 / % 7
28th	2 0 0 7	3 0	2 2	8	427 / % 15
29th	2 0 0 7	1 3	8	5	538 / % 13
30th	2 0 0 8	3 5	2 6	9	926 / % 35
31st	2 0 0 9	4 6	3 9	7	715 / % 46
32nd	2 0 1 0	3 6	2 5	1 1	131 / % 136
33rd	2 0	3 7	2 2	1 5	141 / % 5

	1 1				/	3 7
34th	2 0 1 2	4 0	2 9	1 1	128 1%	
35th	2 0 1 3	3 9	3 1	8	821 /%	
36th	2 0 1 4	4 6	3 6	1 0	522 /%	
37th	2 0 1 5	3 4	2 0	1 4	741 /%	
38th	2 0 1 6	4 8	4 0	8	117 /%	
39th	2 0 1 6	3 5	2 4	1 3	137 3%	
40th	2 0 1 7	4 2	3 0	1 1	126 1%	
41st	2 0 1 8	5 5	3 7	1 8	133 8%	

STPs, it remained as low as 10 PAS officers (such as 25th STP), whereas the highest number of PAS officers in any STP has been 55 probationary officers (41st STP). This table reveals that as compared to the male PAS officers, women's representation in PAS has been on the lower side. However, by looking at Table 1, two trends of women's representation can be determined. One from 1st STP to 27th STP (1979 to 2006) that shows low representation, to the extent of invisibility, for women officers in PAS whereas the second trend shows improved representation of women officers in PAS from 28th STP to 41st STP (2007 to 2018).

Trend 1

For almost three decades (1st STP to 27th STP), women's participation in PAS remained nearly invisible where on average two female officers were inducted in PAS. In contrast, male representation remained extremely prominent during all these years, where on average 26 male officers were inducted in PAS. During five different STPs (11th, 16th, 20th, 21st and 30th STP), no female officer was inducted into PAS and only male PAS officers were inducted during these five years in PAS. During these three decades, only two STPs (such as 14th STP and 27th STP), comparatively, a higher number of female officers, that is 5 and 4 women officers joined PAS respectively.

To determine the trend of women's representation in PAS, Table 1 also shows the ratio of the total number of women PAS officers to the total number of PAS officers during each STP. The ratios in Table 1 confirm that women have been under-represented to the extent of invisibility from 1st STP to 27th STP (1979-2006). It shows low ratios for women's representation such as 1/44 and 1/39 (4th STP and 7th STP respectively). Percentages of the ratios have been drawn that also confirm the under-representation of PAS officers from 1st STP to 27th STP where the average percentage

Prepared by the Author

Source: Pakistan Administrative Campus, Lahore

Table 1 shows that the total strength of PAS officers varies in each STP. During some

ratio remains 6 percent. Figure 1 depicts a pictorial presentation of trend 1.

Figure 1

Figure 1 (Prepared by the Author)
 Source: Table 1

Trend 2

From 28th STP onwards, an upward shift in female representation in PAS can be seen. Ever since 1979, 2006 witnessed the highest women induction in PAS where 08 women probationary officers were inducted. Proceeding years saw a constant upward trend of women's participation, where the maximum number of women participations rose to 18 women probationary officers (41st STP), while the lowest number was 7 women probationary officers (31st STP). Although women's representation in PAS remains low as compared to male PAS officers where on average, 11 female officers were inducted in PAS as compared to 28 male officers who were inducted in PAS during these STPs.

The ratios in Table 1 confirm the fact that women's representation in PAS has improved from 28th STP to 41st STP (2007-2018). It shows some improved ratios for women's representation during the 33rd STP and 37th STP (15/37 and 7/17 respectively). Percentages of the ratios also confirm the

improved representation of PAS officers from 28th STP to 41st STP where the average percentage of the ratio is 25 percent. Figure 2 depicts a pictorial presentation of trend 2.

Figure 2

Figure 2 (Prepared by the Author)
 Source: Table 1

Role of 10 percent quota, 2006 in improved women's representation in PAS

Table 2 shows that during the last 11 STPs (31st STP to 41st STP), there is a consistent upward shift in the women's representation in PAS. One of the factors that is considered a catalyst to increase women's representation in PAS is the 10 percent gender quota, 2006 (Rai et al., 2007). It was applied to the provincial and regional quota allocated for the Civil Services of Pakistan. The quota has been in practice since 2007 when it was first implemented for the women officers of the 31st STP of PAS who qualified CSS examination conducted in the year 2006. Table 2 contains data for 14 different STPs where a 10 percent gender quota, 2006 is implemented for 11 STPs of PAS. It thoroughly analyses the impact of the gender quota 2006 by examining the allocation

of women in PAS on merit seats (open merit as well as provincial merit seats), women quota seats and minority seats. It helps us to understand whether the 10 percent gender quota has contributed towards improved female representation in PAS or not.

Table 2: Impact of gender quota 2006 in improving women representation in PAS (2006-2016)

SPECIALIZED TRAINING PROGRAM (STP)	YEAR OF EXAMINATION	NUMBER OF PAS OFFICERS	NUMBER OF WOMEN PAS OFFICERS	WOMEN PAS OFFICERS ON MERIT	WOMEN PAS OFFICERS ON QUOTA	WOMEN PAS OFFICERS ON MINORITY
31st	2006	35	6	3	3	
32nd	2007	35	15	13	2	
33rd	2008	38	15	8	7	
34th	2009	36	11	8	3	
35th	2010	36	9	6	3	
36th	2011	35	8	5	3	

37th	2012	33	17	13	3	1
38th	2013	36	10	8	1	1
39th	2014	28	12	6	6	
40th	2015	36	10	7	2	1
41st	2016	35	16	14	2	
TOTAL		383	129	91	35	3

Compiled and Prepared by Author

Source: Training-5 wing, Establishment Division, Islamabad

During the year 2006, a total of 35 successful candidates were allocated in PAS, out of which 6 were women candidates. Out of the 6 successful women candidates, 3 candidates were allocated against open and provincial merit quota seats whereas, 3 candidates were allocated on gender quota. If the gender quota had not been implemented in the year 2006, the total number of female PAS officers in the above-mentioned STP would have been 3 female PAS Officers. Similarly, in some years (2008, 2010 and 2014) the impact of women's quota on women's representation in PAS has been so huge that it accounts for a 50% increase in women's representation during that year women's allocation in PAS. Whereas, in some cases, gender quota could not have a significant impact to accelerate women's representation in PAS (such as 2007, 2015 and 2016). Although the impact of women quota varies from STP to STP but Table 2 confirms that it has played an aiding role to improve the numerical representation of women PAS by reserving 35 PAS seats for women that otherwise would have been filled by male candidates.

4.3 Women's representation in key decision-making bureaucratic positions

On average, the career of a PAS officer spans over 30 years to 37 years. During these years he/she attains promotions from the lower and middle echelon to the highest echelon of service that is BPS-22. Traditionally, an officer of PAS is either given a field posting or a posting in the Civil Secretariat. In both cases they are at the helm of affairs that makes them “bureaucratic elites” and one among the six power elites in the country (Ayesha, 2016). These key bureaucratic positions are discussed briefly as under:

Field posting in PAS

PAS officers commonly start their career from a field posting as an Assistant Commissioner (AC) in a Sub-Division/ Tehsil. Later on, after being promoted to senior grades field postings include postings as Additional Deputy Commissioner (ADC), Deputy Commissioner (DC), Additional Commissioner and Commissioner. Historically, posts of AC, DC and Commissioner are considered the most important, powerful and lucrative field postings. Although with time and due to various administrative reforms, the authority associated with these positions has been restructured. Still, these field postings are considered the sought-after and coveted field positions in a PAS career. Therefore, the scope of this study has been restricted to these three key field postings only.

Commissioner: A commissioner is an officer in-charge of general administration and is the Principal Representative of the government in the division (Government of Punjab 2017). He is also a land revenue collector at the divisional level and is custodian of the state land in the division (Land Revenue Act, 1967). In Gilgit-Baltistan and ICT regions, the Commissioner of the division also holds magisterial powers that make them in charge of law and order and security at the Division level.

Deputy Commissioner (DC): Traditionally, the DC was the key stone of the administrative structure in British Administration and was the collector and the District Magistrate at the district level. In modern day, DC is the officer in-charge of the general administration and is the principal representative of the government at the district level (Punjab Civil Administration Act 2017). He/she is also a land revenue collector at the district level and is custodian of state land in the district (Land Revenue Act 1967). In Gilgit-Baltistan and ICT regions, they also hold magisterial powers that make them in charge of law and order and security at the district level.

Assistant Commissioner (AC): AC is the most influential position at the sub-division/tehsil level which is the smallest unit of administration from where a PAS officer usually starts his/her career. AC is the officer in-charge of general administration and is the principal representative of the government at a sub-division/tehsil level (Punjab Civil Administration Act 2017). AC is also a land revenue collector at the tehsil level and is a custodian of the state land in the tehsil (Land Revenue Act, 1967). In Gilgit-Baltistan and ICT regions, they also hold magisterial powers that make them in charge of law and order at the sub-division/tehsil level.

Key positions in the civil secretariat (federal and provincial secretariat)

A PAS officer who can be appointed in the federal and provincial secretariat has the responsibility to formulate policies. An officer of PAS is usually appointed as Deputy Secretary (DS), Joint Secretary (JS), Additional Secretary (AS), Special Secretary (SS), and Secretary within a government department or ministry. For the sake of this study, we examined female representation at top-level positions in the provincial and federal secretariats.

Chief-Secretary (CS): CS is the most desired post in the career of a PAS officer mainly due to the authority, responsibility and prestige associated with this position. In a province, CS is the head of the civil secretariat and is the secretary of the cabinet. He/she supervises activities of all provincial departments and is generally responsible for all matters affecting public tranquillity within the province (Government of Punjab 2011).

Provincial Secretary (PS): The PS is the official head of a provincial department. Usually, officers of PAS in BPS-20 and BPS-21 are posted in this position. PS is chiefly responsible for the efficient administration in the department, to submit proposals for legislation to the cabinet and to execute the sanctioned policy. PS is also responsible for assisting the minister in the formulation of provincial policy (Government of Punjab 2011).

Federal Secretary (FS): FS is the official head of a federal ministry. Usually, officers of PAS in BPS-22 (the highest service grade in the country) are transferred and posted to this prestigious position. An FS is chiefly responsible for the efficient administration in his/her ministry, submits proposals for legislation to the cabinet and executes the sanctioned policies. FS is also responsible to the minister for the business of the ministry and assists him in the formulation of national policies (Government of Punjab 2011).

It is, now essential to know the representation of women (number of women) in the above-mentioned key bureaucratic positions. The representation of women in these key positions clarifies whether there is a mere increase in the number of women at the job-entry level or is it a substantive representation of women in PAS. For this purpose, a detailed breakdown of women's representation in key bureaucratic positions of PAS (from the field as well as the

secretariat) across the country has been prepared. It gives a complete picture of the women PAS officers currently posted in key bureaucratic positions and is helpful in determining the passive representation of women in PAS.

Representation of women PAS officers in key positions in Punjab

Punjab is considered the most developed province in the country with the highest Human Development Index (HDI) and the highest education rate (Najam and Bari 2017). Due to the existence of some best educational institutions, medical facilities and overall better life and work opportunities, Punjab is a preferred place for PAS officers. Currently, 114 women PAS officers are serving all over the Punjab. Table 3 explains in detail how many of them are posted in the key positions (both from field positions and secretariat) within the province of Punjab. Data in table 3 shows that currently no woman PAS officer in BPS-22 is posted in the province. The table further shows, out of 36 positions of provincial secretaries in Punjab, 26 slots have been occupied/held by PAS officers. Out of these 26 positions 22 provincial secretaries are male PAS officers while only 04 secretaries are women PAS officers. The next three columns in the table show the situation of women's representation in key field positions in the province. Currently, there are 09 positions of Commissioners in the province out of which 07 positions have been filled by PAS officers. No woman PAS officer is currently posted against the post of Commissioner in the whole province. Similarly, for the 36 districts in the province, there are 36 positions of DC and the table shows a lower representation of women PAS officers. Out of 36 DC, 22 are from PAS in which 04 women PAS officers are posted as DC while 18 male PAS officers are posted as DC in different districts in the province. The highest representation of women PAS officers can be seen against the post of AC which is the

junior-most field position for a PAS officer. In it, out of 145 positions of AC, 34 PAS officers are posted as AC in different subdivisions/tehsils in the province. The table shows that 20 male and 14 female PAS officers are serving as ACs in the Punjab. Hence, we can interpret from the data that women PAS officers are (well) represented in the junior grades and are under-represented to the point of invisibility in the senior and most important positions in the province.

Table 3: Representation of women PAS officers on key positions in Punjab

Key Positions in the Province	Provincial Secretaries	Chief Secretary	Commissioner	Deputy Commissioner	Assistant Commissioner	
Total Number	2	36	1	9	36	145
Representation of PAS Officers	2	26	1	7	22	34

Representation of Male PAS Officers	2	22	1	7	18	20
Representation of Women PAS Officers	0	4	0	0	4	14

Prepared by the Author

Source: Services and General Administration Department, Government of Punjab

Representation of women PAS officers in key positions in Sindh

Administratively, this province is divided into Urban and Rural Sindh. Karachi, the capital and the biggest urban centre of the province, is home to the provincial secretariat while the districts in the rural Sindh are considered popular destinations for field postings. Table 4 shows women PAS officers in the key positions. Data depicts that currently no woman PAS officer in BPS-22 is posted in the province. Table 4 shows that there are a total 47 positions of provincial secretaries in the province of Sindh. Out of which 15 slots have been occupied/held by PAS officers. Out of these 15 positions, all are being held by male PAS officers. The next three columns in the table show the situation of women's representation in key field positions in the province. Currently, there are 06 positions of Commissioners in the province out of which 50% of the slots that is 3 positions have been filled by PAS officers. No woman PAS officer is currently posted against the post of Commissioner in the whole province. Similarly, there are 29 positions of DCs. Out of these 29 DCs, 13 are from PAS in which one

woman PAS officer is posted as DC. The highest representation of women PAS officers can be seen against the junior-most field position of AC in the province. The table shows that out of 161 positions of ACs, 30 PAS officers are currently posted as ACs out of which 27 are male and 03 female PAS officers. Hence, we concluded from the data that women PAS officers are under-represented to the point of invisibility in important positions in Sindh.

Table 4: Representation of women PAS officers on key positions in Sindh

Key Positions in the Province	Provincial Secretary	Chief Secretary	Commissioner	Deputy Commissioner	Assistant Commissioner
Total Number	1	41	6	29	16
Representation of PAS Officers	1	1	3	12	30
Representation of Male PAS	0	15	3	11	27

Officers					
Representation of Women PAS Officers	10	0	0	1	3

Table prepared by Author

Source: Services and General Administration Department, Government of Sindh

Representation of women PAS officers in key positions in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa

The government of Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa functions according to the Constitution of 1973 (Pasha 2015) and the bureaucratic machinery in the province is headed by the Chief Secretary. Table 5 explains the women PAS officers posted in the key positions within Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa. Data in the table shows that currently no woman PAS officer in BPS-22 is posted in the province. There are a total of 40 positions of PSs in Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa, out of which 13 slots have been occupied by PAS officers. Currently, all these 13 positions of PSs are being filled by male PAS officers and not even a single woman PAS officer is posted as PS in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Similarly, there are 07 positions of Commissioners in the province and there is only one PAS officer (male) who is serving as commissioner in the province. No woman PAS officer is posted as commissioner in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Then, there are 35 positions of DCs, and it shows no representation of women PAS officers. Out of 36 DCs, 20 DCs are from PAS in which not even a single woman PAS officer is posted as DC. The highest representation of women PAS officers can be seen against the post of AC in the province as out of 84 positions of ACs, 17 PAS officers are

posted as ACs. Table 5 shows that 11 male and 06 female PAS officers are serving as ACs in Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa province of Pakistan. Hence, we can interpret from the data that women PAS officers are represented in the junior grade and their representation is absent on other key bureaucratic positions.

Table 5: Representation of women PAS officers on key positions in Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa

Key Positions in the Province	Provincial Secretary	Chief Secretary	Commissioner	Deputy Commissioner	Assistant Commissioner
Total Number	14	1	7	35	84
Representation of PAS Officers	13	1	0	20	17
Representation of Male PAS Officers	13	1	1	20	11
Representation of Women	0	0	0	0	6

en PAS Officers						
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Table prepared by Author

Source: Services and General Administration Department, Government of Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa

Representation of women PAS officers in key positions in Baluchistan

Administratively, Baluchistan is classified as a “hard area” and male PAS officers must serve in the province, a condition associated with their further promotion. Table 6 explains in detail how many women PAS officers are posted on the key bureaucratic positions (both secretariat and field positions) within the province. Data in Table 6 shows that currently, no woman PAS officer in BPS-22 is posted in the province of Baluchistan. The table further shows that there are a total of 36 positions of PS in Baluchistan out of which 02 slots have been occupied/held by male PAS officers. No woman PAS officer is posted as Secretary of a Provincial Department in the Province. Currently, there are 07 positions of Commissioners in the province out of which 04 positions have been filled by PAS officers. No female officer is currently posted against the post of Commissioner in the whole province. Similarly, for the 33 districts in the province, there are 08 positions of DC and there is no representation of women PAS officers against the post of DC in the province. The only representation of women PAS officers can be seen against the post of AC. In it, out of 140 positions of ACs, 13 PAS officers are posted as ACs in different sub-divisions/tehsils in the province. 11 male and only 02 female PAS officers are serving as ACs in the province. Hence, we can interpret from Table 6 that women PAS officers are only represented in the junior grade of AC in the province while their representation is absent in the senior positions in the province.

Table 6: Representation of women PAS officers on key positions in Baluchistan

Key Positions in the Province	Provincial Secretary	Chief Secretary	Commissioner	Deputy Commissioner	Assistant Commissioner	
Total Number	0	36	1	7	33	140
Representation of PAS Officers	0	2	1	4	8	11
Representation of Male PAS Officers	0	2	1	4	8	9
Representation of Women PAS Officers	0	0	0	0	0	2

Table prepared by

Author

Source: Services and General Administration Department, Government of Baluchistan

Representation of women PAS officers in key positions in Gilgit-Baltistan

Table 7 shows that currently no woman PAS officer is posted as a PAS female officer in any of its 34 subdivisions/tehsils. Hence, we can interpret from Table 7 that women PAS officers have no representation in key bureaucratic position in the region of Gilgit-Baltistan as all the positions are occupied by male officers.

Table 7: Representation of women PAS officers on key positions in Gilgit-Baltistan

Key Positions in the Province	Provincial Secretary	Chief Secretary	Commissioner	Deputy Commissioner	Assistant Commissioner	
Total Number	0	24	1	3	10	34
Representation of PAS Officers	0	7	1	2	4	14

cers						
Representation of PAS Male Officers	0	7	1	2	4	14
Representation of Female PAS Officers	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table prepared by Author

Source: Services and General Administration Department, Government of Gilgit-Baltistan

Representation of women PAS officers in key positions in Islamabad Capital Territory (ICT)

Islamabad, the Federal capital of the country, is a distinct constituent unit of the State, under Article 1 of the Constitution of the Islamic Republic of Pakistan. Table 8 shows the details of women PAS officers posted in key positions (both field positions and federal secretariat) in Islamabad. Data reveals that there are a total 24 positions of federal secretaries in the federal secretariat, out of which 20 slots have been occupied/held by PAS officers. Out of these 20 positions, 19 federal secretaries are male PAS officers while only one federal secretary is a woman PAS officer of BPS-22. The most lucrative posts of Chief Commissioner and DC in the district are being held by male PAS officers. The highest representation of women PAS officers can be seen against the post of AC which is the junior-most field position for a PAS officer. Hence, we can interpret from the data that women PAS officers are (well) represented in the junior grades and are under-

represented to the point of invisibility in the senior and most important/lucrative positions in the province.

Table 8: Representation of women PAS officers on key positions in ICT

Key Positions in the Province	Federal Secretary	Chief Commissioner	Deputy Commissioner	Assistant Commissioner
Total Number	24	1	1	6
Representation of PAS Officers	20	1	1	6
Representation of Male PAS Officers	19	1	1	5
Representation of Women PAS Officers	1	0	0	1

Table prepared by Author

Source: Establishment Division, E-5(PAS), Islamabad

Representation of women PAS officers in key positions all over Pakistan

Figure 3 depicts a pictorial presentation of women's representation in PAS across the country in key bureaucratic positions in PAS. The grey bar shows the total number of PAS

representation against the key bureaucratic position, the blue bar shows the representation of male PAS officers on the key bureaucratic positions whereas, the orange bar shows the representation of women PAS officers on these key positions across the country. It confirms that the representation of women PAS officers is concentrated on the lowest grade (Assistant Commissioner) whereas it converts into underrepresentation to the extent of invisibility on higher grades and more important positions.

Figure 3

Figure 3: Representation of women PAS officers on key positions in Pakistan

Discussion

Trends of Women's Representation in PAS

Traditionally, bureaucracy has remained a male-dominated occupation in Pakistan. Despite being half of the total population, women were denied entry into PAS (Chaudhuri, 1969). In Pakistani society, the concept of a working woman is still novel, and there are stereotypical opinions and societal dictates about suitable and decent professions for women (Ansari 2014). Civil Service groups such as PAS are perceived as difficult to manage for women, and a woman's desire to pursue a career in PAS was not initially

tolerable. That is why we see smaller numbers of women allocated to PAS from 1979 to 2006. Another explanation is the discriminatory treatment given to female PAS officers. They were not considered suitable for field jobs, and their presence in key positions, even at the job entry level, such as AC, was rare. They had to work extra hard to compete with their male colleagues from PAS.

However, the dawn of the twenty-first century saw improved numerical representation of women in PAS. Multiple factors such as Constitutional (Article 25 and 27), Legislative (10 percent Gender Quota, 2006), and different policy frameworks (such as the wed-lock policy of 1998 to post women close to their husband's place of posting, no provincial rotation policy for women officers, and paid maternity leave of 90 days) have played a supportive role in encouraging women's induction into PAS (GEPA 2017).

Since there was no literature discussing the trend of women's representation in PAS, the current study aimed to address this issue. A non-reactive document analysis (Neuman, 2006) was employed to develop this study, and the data was collected from three different sources, including the list of PAS officers provided by the Civil Service Academy Lahore, Training Wing T-5, Establishment Division Islamabad, and the offices of Provincial Services and General Administration Departments of all four provinces, and E-5 wing, Establishment Division, Islamabad.

Our results confirmed women's representation in PAS and identified two trends of women's representation. Trend 1 shows that for almost three decades, PAS remained strictly a male-dominated occupation where, on average, only two women officers were allocated to PAS in a batch of 28 probationary officers. Trend 2 shows an upward trend and improved representation of female PAS officers from the 28th STP onwards. It shows a continuous

upward trend till 2018. During the period (2007-2018), even the lowest number of PAS women's representation remains higher than the highest number of female representations in Trend 1. We can say that women's representation in PAS remained low in the initial 27 years, whereas it has improved during the last 11 years. There are several possible explanations for this result.

Role of Gender Quota in Improving Gender Representation

In the last decades, gender representation in decision-making roles has been promoted as a crucial strategy by international platforms such as Beijing, the United Nations, and the Council of Europe (Woodward 2003). Several countries have implemented legislation for gender quotas to ensure democratic governance through improved gender representation (GEPA 2017). Pakistan is one such country that implemented a 10 percent gender quota to promote gender equality in all spheres of its public sector. The 10 percent gender quota in the Civil Services has improved women's representation in PAS. The introduction of the gender quota has played a supportive role in improving women's representation in PAS, which was on the lower side for the last three decades. However, this representation can only be called a numerical increase, and the gender quota seems to have supported women's entrance into PAS.

Women's Representation in Key Positions

To assess women's representation in key bureaucratic positions in PAS, a headcount for key bureaucratic positions in the country was conducted in this research. The purpose was to know if women's representation in PAS is at par with the representation of male PAS officers. It supports the existing literature on the subject that women in Pakistan have constitutional and legal protection to move vertically in their careers as their male colleagues do. The presence of a woman PAS

officer in the post

of FS shows that women are promoted to higher positions.

However, the under-representation of women PAS officers to the extent of invisibility in key bureaucratic positions also supports our proposition that in PAS, women theoretically have no barriers to join the service, but they do not get equal opportunities for full participation and posting in key bureaucratic positions. These results confirm the notion that Pakistan's bureaucracy is still male-coded, where the most lucrative and key bureaucratic positions are held by male counterparts. Results for the 286 key bureaucratic positions studied from all over the country in this study show that 250 key bureaucratic positions have been occupied by male PAS officers, while only 36 key bureaucratic positions have been occupied by women PAS officers. It is interesting to note that 66% of these key bureaucratic positions occupied by women PAS officers are concentrated at the junior-most key bureaucratic position of AC. This proves our proposition that women PAS officers are concentrated at the job entry level alone, and despite having no restriction on women joining PAS, women officers in PAS are concentrated in the lower grades and are almost invisible in the middle to higher echelons of bureaucratic power.

The conventional explanation given for this disparity in men's and women's representation in key bureaucratic positions in PAS is that women officers themselves opt for side positions and stay away from the responsibility of key bureaucratic positions. This argument has been supported in the context that women in Pakistan have to bear family responsibilities, especially children. However, this may not be the complete truth and should not be used as a justification. In the recent past, several instances support that women PAS officers accepted the responsibility of key bureaucratic positions and outshone when they got an opportunity. One such instance can be from the

general elections of 2018 in the district of Khushab, Pakistan. A woman PAS DC and a woman PAS AC not only conducted general elections for five slots of the national and provincial assembly successfully but also put in efforts for women to cast their votes for the first time in 70 years (Women Voters Make History 2018).

Another disparity we have seen is in terms of provinces, where some provinces show more women's representation than others. An explanation in this regard can be that Punjab is the most developed province with the highest HDI ranking and education rate in the country (Pakistan National Human Development Report 2017). Although in the case of Punjab, some representation in upper echelons such as PS can be seen, still, the major concentration of women PAS officers can be found in the junior-most key bureaucratic position of AC. Since the security situation for the Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa and Baluchistan provinces remained uncertain, it can be assumed that women PAS officers are not posted in these provinces in key bureaucratic positions due to security reasons. However, Gilgit-Baltistan, being the most peaceful place in the country, has no representation of women officers in key bureaucratic positions. Since bureaucracies work in a larger environment, it will be enlightening to further explore the results of this study with the social, cultural, and political dynamics of these provinces.

Conclusion

The current study investigated the trend of women's representation in one of the most prestigious cadres of the Civil Services of Pakistan, which was created as a result of the 1973 administrative reforms. The investigation revealed that over the period of 1973-2018, women's numerical representation in PAS has increased (which was non-existent before the administrative reform). Factors such as the gender quota have played a positive role in accelerating women's representation in PAS at

the job entry level.

However, meaningful passive representation of women in PAS is still a long way to go. Currently, women in PAS face no barriers in terms of allocation in PAS, vertical career growth, and remuneration. However, women are denied full participation in PAS, which is evident from the fact that they are under-represented to the level of invisibility in key bureaucratic positions in PAS. The traditional notion that women are not suitable for fieldwork and are more suitable for desk jobs has caused the ostracism of women in decision-making in PAS, and this is clear in the case of the current study.

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